

The Effectiveness of the Legislative Function in Drafting Local Regulations: A Case Study of the Madiun City Regional House of Representatives (DPRD) 2019-2024

F. Bagus Panuntun¹, Sarjiyati², Sigit Sapto Nugroho³, Krista Yitawati⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Faculty of Law, Universitas Merdeka Madiun, Madiun 63133, East Java, Indonesia

ABSTRACT:

Objective: This research analyzes the legal effectiveness of local regulation formulation by the Regional House of Representatives (DPRD) of Madiun City for the 2019–2024 period.

Method: The research method employed is empirical or sociological legal research, utilizing both primary and secondary data sources, which are subsequently analyzed using a descriptive qualitative approach.

Findings: The results indicate that, based on the analysis of legal effectiveness theory, the local regulations formulated by the Madiun City DPRD during the 2019–2024 period reflect high substantial quality in their legal products, which are firmly grounded in the foundational principles of legislation formulation, namely: (1) philosophical foundations, (2) sociological foundations, and (3) juridical foundations. From a structural law perspective, the local regulation formulation executed by the DPRD and the Madiun City Government demonstrates active existence and the proper fulfillment of their core duties and functions, as evidenced by: (1) the synergy in the legislative function between the DPRD and the Executive branch, and (2) the functioning of check and balance mechanisms. In terms of legal culture which encompasses the values, attitudes, awareness, and opinions of both the public and policymakers toward the operation of law the study highlights: (1) open public participation, (2) a pro-people political commitment, and (3) public compliance, wherein the law-abiding culture of Madiun City residents facilitates smoother implementation of regulations on the ground.

KEYWORDS: Legal Effectiveness; Local Regulation Formulation; DPRD; Madiun City; Legislation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The administration of local government within a democratic constitutional state positions local regulations (Peraturan Daerah / Perda) as strategic legal instruments for governing community life within regions. The existence of local regulations is not merely a manifestation of the principle of regional autonomy as mandated by Article 18 of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, but also serves as a vehicle to realize public services, regional development, and the protection of public interests. Consequently, the formulation process of local regulations must be executed effectively, qualitatively, and in accordance with the principles of good legislation formulation.¹

Local Government refers to the administration of governmental affairs by the local government and the regional house of representatives (DPRD) in accordance with the principles of regional autonomy and co-administration tasks, exercising the widest possible autonomy within the system and principles of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia as stipulated in the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia.² In relation to this matter, local government constitutes the executor of local government

¹ Nugroho, S. S., Sarjiyati, & Sarbini. (2024). *The Constitutional State and Democracy: Conceiving a Pancasila-Based Constitutional State*. Underline

² Article 1 of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 23 of 2014 concerning Local Government

³ Puspitaningrum, J. (2025). *Local Government Law and Special Autonomy*. PT. Sonpedia Publishing Indonesia.

functions carried out by local government institutions, specifically the Local Executive (the regional government) and the Regional House of Representatives (DPRD). The administration of local government is executed by the DPRD and the Regional Head, both

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of whom serve as components of the local government administration, mandated by the people to administer the governmental affairs devolved to the region.³ The DPRD and the Regional Head hold positions as partners with distinct functions. The DPRD functions in the formulation of local regulations (Peraturan Daerah / Perda), budgeting, and oversight, whereas the Regional Head executes the function of implementing local regulations and regional policies.

Pursuant to the provisions of Article 18 Paragraph (6) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, regional governments reserve the right to enact local regulations and other directives to execute regional autonomy and co-administration tasks. Furthermore, Article 242 Paragraph (1) of Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Local Government stipulates that a draft local regulation shall be jointly approved by the DPRD and the Regional Head to be enacted into law as a local regulation. Similarly, under Articles 317 and 366 of Law Number 17 of 2014 concerning the MPR, DPR, DPD, and DPRD, the DPRD possesses the authority and duty to formulate local regulations, as well as to deliberate and approve local regulations jointly with the Regional Head.

Within the context of regional autonomy, the Regional House of Representatives (DPRD) holds a pivotal legislative function. This function is manifested through the joint formulation of local regulations with the regional head, as mandated by Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Local Government. Through this legislative function, the DPRD is demanded to be capable of producing regional legal products that are responsive to public needs and adaptable in accommodating the social, economic, and cultural developments occurring within the region.¹ The effectiveness of executing the DPRD's legislative function serves as a crucial indicator in assessing the success of local government administration that is both democratic and public interest-oriented.

The function of local regulation formulation within the Regency/City DPRD, as stipulated in Article 2 of the Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 12 of 2018 concerning Guidelines for Drafting Standing Orders of Provincial, Regency, and City Regional Houses of Representatives, is inherently inseparable from legal policy (politik hukum). According to Mahfud M.D., legal policy refers to the official and legitimate policy framework concerning the laws to be enacted, implemented either through the creation of new laws or the replacement of existing ones, in order to achieve national objectives.² In essence, issues within legal politics encompass legal substance, legal structure, and legal culture. Persistent inconsistencies in legislation—such as ambiguous legislative drafting and the absence of necessary implementing regulations—hinder practical implementation. It is in this regard that legal politics plays a pivotal role in fostering regulations capable of establishing a transparent, independent, and impartial legal system. Ultimately, the existence of legislation and the precise formulation of legal provisions serve as the bridge between established legal policy and its execution in practice.³

The formulation of local regulations is inherently a legal process involving various stages, ranging from planning, drafting, deliberation, facilitation, and evaluation, to enactment. Each stage requires the support of competent human resources, effective inter-institutional coordination, and an adequate understanding of legislative drafting techniques. If any of these elements is unfulfilled, both the quality and quantity of the resulting regional legal products are potentially subject to hindrances.⁴

In the function of local regulation formulation, the performance enhancement of the DPRD is not solely measured by the quantity of local regulations (Peraturan Daerah / Perda) produced. Rather, the DPRD's quality in executing this legislative function is indicated by the substance of the local regulations, which ought to predominantly favor the interests of the public at large. In drafting local regulations, DPRD members should actively serve as a primary source of concepts and ideas, in accordance with their standing as political actors.

The DPRD is granted the authority to formulate local regulations (Peraturan Daerah / Perda) jointly with the Regional Government. This function is exercised through the DPRD's right of initiative and right of amendment. This local regulation formulation function needs to be optimized, as it represents policy formulation rooted in public aspirations (bottom-up policy making). However, in its practical implementation, numerous issues are frequently encountered regarding the formulation process. These include a lack of public participation, the fact that many DPRD members still do not exercise their right of initiative, the persistent political interests of individual council members during the formulation process, and the vested interests of other stakeholders outside the DPRD and the Regional Government in proposing a local regulation.⁵

⁴ Sarbini, & Nugroho, S. S. (2023). *The Welfare State within the Framework of Pancasila*. Lakeisha

⁵ Mastorat, M., & Ridwan, R. (2025). *Legal Politics in Indonesia*. AMU Press

³ Nugroho, S. S., Haryani, A. T., & Purnama, T. Y. (2024). The Effectiveness of Regulations on Cultural Tourism Development Based on the Martial Arts Industry in Madiun City, East Java: A Legal System Theory Perspective. *Dinamika Hukum*, 25(1), 57–64

⁶ Purnama, T. Y., Nugroho, S. S., & Rahardjo, M. (2023). Implementation of the DPRD's Oversight Function in Realizing Good Local Governance. *Yustisia Merdeka: Jurnal Ilmiah Hukum*, 9(1), 59–67.

⁷ Harsanti, E. I. (2025). The Role of the Madiun City Regional House of Representatives in Drafting Local Regulations (A Study of the Madiun City DPRD 2019–2024) [Master's thesis, Widyagama University of Malang]. Widyagama University of Malang Repository

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Based on preliminary observations regarding the drafting of Madiun City local regulations, a total of 43 (forty-three) local regulations were enacted by the Madiun City Government with the approval of the Madiun City Regional House of Representatives (DPRD) during the 2019–2024 period. In relation to the drafting and enactment of these regulations, practice often illustrates how council members become deeply engrossed in drafting intricate and substantive details of a regulation without possessing adequate expertise. This occasionally leads to prolonged debates over matters where members share a mutual lack of understanding regarding the underlying substance, ultimately consuming valuable time without achieving an optimal resolution. The DPRD faces numerous challenges in executing its duties, including local situations and conditions, internal institutional weaknesses within the DPRD, and a conflict of interest between un-devolved central government authorities and the public aspirations that must be voiced.

Research regarding the effectiveness of local regulation formulation within the Madiun City DPRD is crucial to conduct, as there remains a scarcity of empirical studies specifically examining the execution of the DPRD's legislative function at the municipal level with a focus on hindering factors and applicable solutions. Most prior studies have predominantly highlighted the normative aspects of local regulation formulation or evaluated the substance of the resulting regulations. Consequently, this study seeks to address this research gap through an empirical approach that emphasizes the effectiveness of the local regulation formulation process in practice.⁶

The urgency of this research is increasingly relevant considering that the quality of regional regulations has a direct impact on the effectiveness of governance and public services. Regulations formulated through an effective process will yield legal certainty, enhance the quality of public governance, and strengthen the accountability of regional legislative institutions. Conversely, an ineffective regulatory formulation process has the potential to generate legal uncertainty and hinder the achievement of regional development objectives.

Based on the aforementioned rationale, this research aims to analyze the legal effectiveness of local regulation formulation within the Madiun City DPRD for the 2019–2024 period and to identify the various factors that hinder the formulation process. Furthermore, this study formulates applicable solutions to enhance the quality and effectiveness of the DPRD's legislative function, thereby enabling the production of regional legal products that are more responsive, qualitative, and aligned with public needs.

METHOD

The methodology employed in this study is empirical legal research, also known as socio-legal research, which examines applicable legal provisions alongside their actual execution within society.⁷ Empirical legal research is an inquiry conducted into the actual or real-world conditions occurring within society, through which the practical operation of law (law in action) can be observed. This approach aims to uncover and identify facts and data; once the data is gathered, problem identification is performed, subsequently leading to the formulation of targeted resolutions.⁸

The data sources utilized in this research comprise primary and secondary data. Primary data consists of the researcher's direct observations at the Madiun City DPRD and interviews conducted with key informants, including several DPRD members, the Secretary of the Council (Sekretaris Dewan), and expert staff. Secondary data encompasses primary legal materials, namely the relevant legislation, as well as secondary legal materials, which include journals, books, and other reference materials. Subsequently, the data is analyzed using a descriptive-qualitative approach along with the deductive method to draw conclusions that address the core research questions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Legal Effectiveness of Local Regulation Formulation within the Madiun City DPRD (2019–2024) :

Local regulation (Peraturan Daerah / Perda) formulation serves as a core function of the DPRD in discharging its legislative duties, as mandated by Law Number 23 of 2014 on Regional Government. This legislative role is operationalized through the compilation of the Regional Regulation Formulation Program (Propemperda), the deliberation of draft regional regulations (Raperda), and the ultimate enactment of these regulations alongside the regional head. From a constitutional state perspective (rechtsstaat), local regulations possess a strategic standing; they act as legal instruments designed to regulate regional governance while simultaneously providing a statutory foundation for local public policy implementation.

Bagir Manan states that the functions of legislation can be classified into two primary categories, namely :⁹ (1) Internal Function, which refers to the role of regulations within the framework of the legal system (statutory law) toward the internal structure of legal norms. Legislation plays a role in law creation, law reform, the integration of legal pluralism, and providing legal certainty. The

⁸ *Ibid*

⁹ Nugroho, S. S., Haryani, A. T., & Farkhani. (2020). *Legal Research Methodology*. Oase Pustaka

¹⁰ Nugroho, S. S. (2025). *Introduction to Legal Research Methods*. Underline

¹¹ Manan, B. (2020). *Welcoming the Dawn of Regional Autonomy*. PSH Fakultas Hukum UII

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internal functions of legislation include: (a) the function of law creation; (b) the function of law reform; (c) the function of integrating the pluralism of the legal system; and (d) the function of legal certainty. (2) External Function, which refers to the relationship between legislation and the societal context in which it is applied. This external function can be regarded as the social function of law, encompassing roles in social change, stabilization, and legal facilitation. Consequently, this function is also applicable to customary law (hukum adat), customary practices, or jurisprudential law.

In Indonesia, legislation tends to play a primary role in this social function, in alignment with the aforementioned considerations. This social function can be categorized into: (a) the function of social change; (b) the function of stabilization; and (c) the function of legal facilitation.

The genesis of a local regulation stems from the local government's initiative to manage regional autonomy in compliance with the provisions set forth in the 2014 Regional Government Law. This aims to establish a legal framework that regulates societal activities so that they do not operate without boundaries. This restriction is not intended to enforce repressive measures that violate human rights, but rather constitutes an effort to provide legal certainty to its citizens, ensuring they feel supported, protected, and recognized in their existence.

Local regulations (Perda) constitute a form of legal regulation situated at the lowest level within the hierarchy of legislation. They possess the broadest scope of material substance yet exhibit limited flexibility, as they must align with the regulations superior to them. This concept can be interpreted through the Stufenbau theory introduced by Hans Kelsen, which posits that positive law (regulations) is structured in a tiered and hierarchical manner; lower regulations derive their validity from and must not conflict with higher regulations, a principle known as the legal maxim *lex superior derogat legi inferiori*.¹⁰

From an alternative perspective, local regulations are also viewed as instruments that reflect the values embedded within a regional society. This allows the material substance of a local regulation to accommodate local interests and conditions, without disregarding the defining characteristics of Indonesian law, namely: (a) the element of command; (b) the element of prohibition; (c) the element of permission; (d) the application of strict sanctions; and (e) commands and prohibitions that must be obeyed.¹¹

As an integral part of the prevailing Indonesian legal system, local regulations (Perda) ought to reflect a cohesive legal force aligned with other legislation, while concurrently acting as a safeguard for Indonesia's status as a constitutional state (*rechtsstaat*), despite emerging and applying within an autonomous region. A system is defined as an organized and complex whole, comprising a collection or integration of parts that form a comprehensive unity. Since these regions constitute parts of the legal territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI) which adheres to the rule of law, the presence of regional legal products is highly imperative to support the implementation of regional autonomy.¹²

The procedures for formulating a local regulation, undertaken jointly by the DPRD and the regional head, must refer to several related legislations. As part of the planning for both Provincial and Regency/City Regional Regulation Formulation Programs (Propemperda), the drafting process must be carried out in a planned, systematic, and integrated manner, adhering to: (a) Law Number 12 of 2011 concerning the Formulation of Legislation, juncto Law Number 15 of 2019 concerning the Amendment to Law Number 12 of 2011; (b) Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government; (c) Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2014 concerning the Implementing Regulation of Law Number 12 of 2011 concerning the Formulation of Legislation; and (d) Minister of Home Affairs Regulation (Permendagri) Number 80 of 2015 concerning the Formulation of Regional Legal Products, along with Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 120 of 2018 concerning the Amendment to Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 80 of 2015. Furthermore, the objectives of establishing procedures for local regulation formulation, specifically within the DPRD environment, are: (a) to create procedures that are clear-directed and wellplanned; (b) to form integrated and coordinated local regulations as part of regional legal development; (c) to provide a working foundation that facilitates tasks for members of the Regional House of Representatives (DPRD), the DPRD Secretariat, and the regional government; (d) to establish local regulations that serve as a foundation and cohesive bond for other development sectors, while implementing the function of law as a tool of development engineering and a preventive instrument; and (e) to achieve integrated and unified dispute resolution and behavioral regulation.¹⁶

Based on the research findings, the execution of the legislative function by the Madiun City DPRD for the 2019–2024 period was generally quite effective. This is evident from the total number of local regulations enacted during the period, which amounted to 70 Perda. This achievement demonstrates a relatively strong legislative productivity compared to the annual targets set in the Regional Regulation Formulation Program (Propemperda). The Madiun City DPRD, in collaboration with the Madiun City

¹² Purnama, T. Y., Nugroho, S. S., & Rahardjo, M. 2023. *Op-Cit*, p.p.59-67.

¹³ Fitria, R. A., Hasan, A., Umar, M., & Khasyi'in, N. (2024). The Dynamics of Legal Politics in Formulating Local Regulations: Between Local and National Interests. *Indonesian Journal of Islamic Jurisprudence, Economic and Legal Theory*, 2(2), 833–853.

¹⁴ Nugroho, S. S., & Pradhana, A. P. (2026). Integration of local wisdom and the existence of customary law in climate change mitigation policies. *Sahaja: Journal Sharia and Humanities*, 5(1), 51–58 ¹⁶ Errysta Ida harsanti, 2025, *Op-Cit*, p.p. 67

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Government, consistently conducted deliberations on draft local regulations (Raperda), arising from both executive proposals and legislative initiatives.

Sociologically, the success of the Madiun City DPRD in producing 70 local regulations during the 2019–2024 period demonstrates that its legislative function was performed reasonably well. However, a number of draft local regulations (Raperda) experienced delays in enactment due to the facilitation and harmonization processes, which required a considerable amount of time. This condition caused several Raperda to be deferred from enactment within the same fiscal year as their deliberation, thereby requiring their continuation into the following year.

Based on the research findings as explained by the Bapemperda (Regional Regulation Formulation Body), the local regulation formulation function of the Madiun City DPRD for the 2019–2024 period operated optimally. This is evidenced by the productivity of Bapemperda in deliberating and enacting local regulations over the past five years, totaling 70 Perda. The Madiun City DPRD is considered productive by the Legal Bureau of the Regional Secretariat of East Java Province compared to DPRDs from other regions in East Java. In addition to drafting and deliberating Raperda, the Bapemperda of the Madiun City DPRD also exercises an oversight function regarding local regulations by routinely conducting Local Regulation Evaluations, which has become a regular annual program.

Pursuant to the theoretical framework of the operation of law (legal effectiveness theory), law must be conceptualized as a system wherein every legal system invariably comprises three components: the legal substance, the legal structure, and the legal culture.¹³ In terms of legal substance, the formulation of local regulations by the Madiun City DPRD has been executed in compliance with the prevailing provisions. As a substantial system, it determines whether or not a law can be implemented. Substance also refers to the products generated by actors within the legal system, which encompass the decisions they issue and the new rules they draft in the form of local regulations. Structurally, the legal structure of a system comprises various institutions created by that system, along with their diverse functions to support its operation; in this regard, the Madiun City DPRD serves institutionally as the body responsible for formulating regulations, having produced 70 local regulations over a five-year period. Meanwhile, the legal culture is closely intertwined with public legal awareness. Higher public legal awareness fosters a positive legal culture capable of shifting the public's long-standing perception of the law. Simply put, the level of public compliance with the law serves as an indicator of its functionality; in this context, public participation in providing inputs, suggestions, and critiques during public hearings and the drafting of local regulations remains the key to the existing legal culture.¹⁴

Consequently, based on the indicators of legislative productivity, compliance with statutory formulation procedures, and the success of the DPRD and the Madiun City Government in producing 70 local regulations during the 2019–2024 period, the formulation of local regulations by the Madiun City DPRD can be categorized as reasonably effective. Nonetheless, this effectiveness has not yet reached an optimal level due to persisting constraints within human resources and institutional support.

The primary obstacle arising in the local regulation formulation process within the Madiun City DPRD is the variation in human resource quality among its members, stemming from diverse and sometimes mismatched educational backgrounds. There is a distinct shortage of legal education backgrounds among the DPRD members; as a representative body, its members are drawn from various segments of society with disparate educational levels, resulting in very few holding a formal background in law. Consequently, since the drafting of a local regulation fundamentally requires sound psychological and philosophical rationales, a lack of basic legal and scientific expertise poses a significant challenge. This deficiency ultimately prevents comprehensive and mature deliberations, contrasting sharply with the executive branch, whose draft regulations (Raperda) are prepared by a more seasoned legal division. Furthermore, if the council members—particularly those within the special committee (Pansus)—lack a profound understanding of the law, it will severely hinder the smoothness and maturity of the entire legislative deliberation process. Another impeding factor is the shortage of legislative drafters within the Madiun City DPRD, which currently employs only a single individual. Although Law Number 12 of 2011 explicitly mandates that the drafting and deliberation of draft local regulations (Raperda) must involve professional legislative drafters, the presence of only one legislative drafter within the DPRD Secretariat severely limits the capacity to optimize the legislative drafting process.

Based on the research findings, several solutions or problem-solving measures can be proposed to address the aforementioned obstacles encountered in the local regulation formulation process within the Madiun City DPRD for the 2019–2024 period, including: (1) establishing collaborations with universities that possess competent experts in the field of law, thereby extensively involving legal experts from both public and private higher education institutions who specialize in legal drafting during the formulation and deliberation of Raperda; (2) addressing the second obstacle by maximizing consultation and coordination with the Legal Bureau of the Regional Secretariat of East Java Province, as well as initiating meetings or audiences to expedite the completion

¹⁵ Nugroho, S. S., Haryani, A. T., & Purnama, T. Y. (2024). Cultural Tourism Regulation Based on the Pencak Silat Industry in Madiun City, East Java. *FUNDAMENTAL: JURNAL ILMIAH HUKUM*, 13(1), 71–82.

¹⁶ Yitawati, K., & Nugroho, S. S. (2026). The Legal Effectiveness of Official Vehicle Auctions at the Madiun State Asset Management and Auction Office. *Dinamika Hukum*, 27(1), 68–84

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and submission of the facilitated Raperda to the DPRD; and (3) resolving the third obstacle by requesting additional personnel holding functional positions as legislative drafters from the BKPSDM (Regional Civil Service and Human Resources Development Agency), while simultaneously collaborating with legislative drafters from the Legal Division of the Regional Secretariat during Raperda deliberations.¹⁵

To support the effectiveness of local regulation formulation by the Madiun City DPRD during the 2019–2024 period, the role of the DPRD Secretariat was highly critical in preparing the necessary instruments for the council members to execute their legislative duties. These roles include: (1) the DPRD Secretariat's role in facilitating the council's regulation formulation function, wherein the Secretariat maintains a Subdivision for Legislative Studies specifically tasked with accommodating all of the DPRD's logistical and substantive needs in enacting regulations. The Subdivision for Legislative Studies manages an action program consisting of two sub-activities: the deliberation of draft local regulations (Raperda) and the study of legislation, both encompassing various activities that represent the realization of the DPRD's local regulation formulation function; and (2) additionally, the DPRD Secretariat secures budgetary allocations for the Subdivision for Legislative Studies within the Regional Budget (APBD) to execute these planned programs and activities.

Pursuant to the legal effectiveness theory analysis, the local regulations produced by the Madiun City DPRD—encompassing both legislative initiatives and executive proposals from the Madiun City Government—reflect high quality as substantial legal products. These regulations are fundamentally grounded in the primary pillars of statutory formulation, which include: (1) the philosophical foundation, which dictates that the formulated regulations must incorporate the worldview, consciousness, and legal ideals encompassing the spiritual milieu and national philosophy of Indonesia, derived from Pancasila and the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia; (2) the sociological foundation, which ensures that the regulations are drafted to satisfy societal needs across various aspects; and (3) the juridical foundation, which grants the competent institutions the authority to enact specific regulations. Materially, the juridical foundation serves as the substantive legal basis to regulate specific matters, whereas technically, it establishes the formal mandate regarding the procedures for legislative formulation.

From a structural legal perspective, the formulation of local regulations undertaken by the DPRD and the Madiun City Government demonstrates their existence and the execution of their core duties and functions in statutory drafting, which include: (1) Synergy between Legislative and Executive Functions: This component operates optimally through productive collaboration between the Regional Regulation Formulation Body (Bapemperda) of the Madiun City DPRD and the Madiun City Government; and (2) Check and Balance Mechanism: The legal structure involves mandatory assistance, supervision, and facilitation processes by the East Java Provincial Government (the Governor) prior to the official enactment of a local regulation. An adaptive bureaucracy ensures that the administrative process for both legislative initiatives and executive proposals proceeds smoothly.

From a legal culture perspective, this dimension encompasses the values, attitudes, awareness, and opinions of both the public and policymakers toward the operation of law. The elements of this legal culture include: (1) Open Public Participation, wherein the legislative process incorporates public hearings, public consultation meetings (RDP), and periodic dissemination. This participatory legal culture accommodates inputs from community leaders, academics, professional associations, and local communities to ensure that the resulting regulations gain robust social legitimacy; (2) Pro-People Political Commitment, reflecting that the members of the Madiun City DPRD possess high legal awareness and a strong political commitment to achieve the targets set in the Regional Regulation Formulation Program (Propemperda) for the benefit of the citizens of the Kota Pendekar (Warrior City); and (3) Public Compliance, meaning that the law-abiding culture among Madiun City residents facilitates the implementation of regulations on the ground. When the public feels genuinely involved and local regulations are perceived as just, social resistance can be minimized to the furthest extent possible.¹⁶

CONCLUSION

Pursuant to the legal effectiveness theory analysis, the local regulations formulated by the Madiun City DPRD for the 2019–2024 period reflect high quality as substantial legal products, which are fundamentally grounded in the primary pillars of statutory formulation: (1) the philosophical foundation, (2) the sociological foundation, and (3) the juridical foundation. From a structural legal perspective, the formulation of local regulations undertaken by the DPRD and the Madiun City Government demonstrates their operational existence and the execution of their core duties and functions, notably evidenced by: (1) the synergy between the legislative and executive functions, and (2) the integration of a check-and-balance mechanism. Furthermore, within the legal culture dimension—which encompasses the values, attitudes, awareness, and opinions of both the public and policymakers toward the operation of law—the process is characterized by: (1) open public participation, (2) a pro-people political commitment, and (3)

¹⁷ Errysta Ida Harsanti, 2025, *Op-Cit*, p.p. 89

¹⁸ Arthanto, R. B., & Nugroho, S. S. (2025). Implementasi of public information disclosure regulations in an electronicbased government system in Madiun City. *Yustisia Merdeka: Jurnal Ilmiah Hukum*, 11(2), 42–52

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public compliance, wherein a law-abiding culture among Madiun City residents significantly facilitates the implementation of regulations on the ground.

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